

EOSC Observatory Operational Level Agreement

Status	Final
Agreement between	EOSC Future and service suppliers OpenAIRE and Technopolis Group Belgium of the EOSC Observatory

Document Log

Version	Date	Comment	Author
0.1	14 July 2022	This agreement has been adopted from the EOSC-Core Participation Agreement V1.0 (dated 21 June 2022)	Gareth O’Neill
1.0	24 April 2023	The agreement has been updated to be in line with current developments and implementation of EOSC Observatory	Gareth O’Neill, Stefania Martziou, and Alessandro Paolini

This EOSC Observatory Operational Level Agreement (‘the Agreement’) is an indication of intent made between the **EOSC Future project** and the service suppliers **OpenAIRE** and **Technopolis Group Belgium** to define the provision and support of the provided service components of the EOSC Observatory (‘the Observatory’) as described hereafter.

The scope of this Agreement is for service provision within the EOSC Future project. Activities and obligations of beneficiaries are covered by the Grant Agreement of this project. This Agreement does not replace the Grant Agreement but exists alongside it, relating solely to the provision and support of services within the project. This activity covers the development and implementation of the Observatory in EOSC Future WP2/T2.3 and collaborates with WP7/T7.4.

The Service

This Agreement defines the delivery of the services described as follows:

<p>Description</p>	<p>The Observatory is an EOSC Support Service for monitoring the implementation and uptake of EOSC and Open Science. This policy intelligence tool supports the research community in determining the state-of-play and tracking the progress of EOSC and Open Science as well as stakeholders in developing policies and practices for EOSC and Open Science.</p> <p>The Observatory is being developed by OpenAIRE and Technopolis Group Belgium in the EOSC Future project. The tool consists of a platform hosted on a website which has two sides: a closed back end which collects data on EOSC and Open Science and a public front end which presents this collected data.</p> <p>The back end consists of: a survey tool for EOSC Future administrators to create and manage surveys aimed at targeted stakeholders; an internal dashboard for those stakeholders to respond to surveys and manage their own responses as well as to visualise and exploit collected data; a database of the collected data from the surveys and key external data sources.</p> <p>The collected data feeds into the front end which consists of a public dashboard where users can visualise and exploit the collected data on the website of the Observatory. The dashboard presents the data at national and European levels as well as across key thematic categories for EOSC and Open Science.</p> <p>The surveys that will be run through the survey tool form primary data that is qualitative and quantitative. The respondents will be key EOSC stakeholders, including Member States and Associated countries (MS/AC) in the EOSC Steering Board (EOSC-SB) and national experts on EOSC and Open Science.</p> <p>Quantitative data will also be collected from existing trusted data sources to complement the survey data. This externally collected data will be harvested automatically from sources such as the OpenAIRE Research Graph and EOSC Portal and will allow a snapshot at any given moment as well as an annual and multi-annual overview of the implementation and uptake of EOSC and Open Science across Europe.</p>
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The suppliers agree to fulfil the following obligations:

<p>Coordination</p>	<p>The suppliers are responsible for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Liaising with Cyfronet to coordinate the hosting and deployment of the Observatory on a virtual machine provided by Cyfronet on a Cyfronet server and mapping the Observatory subdomain on the EOSC Portal domain [https://eoscobservatory.eosc-portal.eu] to the server IP address provided by Cyfronet ● Coordinating regular meetings with EOSC-SB and EOSC-A to align surveys and policies and tailor the functionality of the Observatory ● Liaising with EOSC-SB to coordinate the annual survey on National Contributions to EOSC among the members of EOSC-SB ● Liaising with national experts to coordinate an annual survey which will provide additional national data on EOSC and Open Science.
<p>Operational</p>	<p>The suppliers are responsible for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Developing and running the software for the technical operation of the Observatory ● Managing the rights of users to be able to access and utilise the Observatory ● Running the annual survey on National Contributions to EOSC among EOSC-SB members to collect and report on responses ● Running the annual survey on EOSC and Open Science activities among national experts to collect additional national data ● Publishing data in the Observatory which is adequately visible and exploitable for users ● Managing the deployment of the Observatory software and underlying components on the virtual machine (e.g. index and database) ● Managing the back-up policy for Cyfronet to back up the Observatory database (e.g. back-up approach, frequency, and restoration).

Maintenance	<p>The internal supplier is responsible for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fixing bugs and maintaining the software for the technical operation of the Observatory ● Gathering the requirements of users to improve the functionality of the Observatory ● Updating the functionality of the Observatory according to the changing needs of users ● Providing and archiving adequate end user documentation for the Observatory.
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Service Hours

IT services according to the service catalogue are delivered during 24 hours per day and 7 days per week (i.e. 365 days or 8,760 hours) for the seamless support of business operations.

The following exceptions apply:

- Planned maintenance windows or service interruptions ('scheduled downtimes') shall be notified in a timely manner, i.e. at least 24 hours prior to the start of the outage, using a method appropriate for the service (e.g. email, banner, social media)
- Live support is provided during support hours as defined below.

Technical Support

Technical support is provided by the Observatory support team through the technical mailing list for all technical queries by users related to the Observatory <eoscobservatory@openaire.eu>.

Support is available between Monday and Friday from 09.00 and 17.00 CE(S)T. This excludes public holidays and other days when the host organisation(s) providing the service are closed. During these times, support will be provided on a best-effort basis, and any foreseen downtime will be declared in the EOSC Topology Grid Configuration Database (GOCDB) [<https://gocdb.eosc-portal.eu/portal/index.php>].

Incident Handling

Incidents will be handled according to the quality of support level that is defined by EOSC Future according to the impact of the outage or service quality degradation.

The quality of support levels are defined as follows:

Base level: defines a response time via email of 5 working days regardless of the priority

Medium level:

Incident priority	Response time
Low	5 working days
Medium	3 working days
High	1 working day

Advanced level:

Incident priority	Response time
Low	5 working days
Medium	1 working day
High	4 working hours

Response time is provided as a service level target.

Service Requests

In addition to resolving incidents, standard service requests (e.g. change requests, information requests, and documentation) will be fulfilled through the support unit defined above in the same way as incidents. Service requests are classified as 'low'.

Service Level Targets

Monthly availability:

- Defined as the ability of a service or service component to fulfil its intended function at a specific time or over a calendar month
- Minimum (as a percentage per month): 95%.

Monthly reliability:

- Defined as the ability of a service or service component to fulfil its intended function at a specific time or over a calendar month, excluding scheduled maintenance periods
- Minimum (as a percentage per month): 98%.

Quality of support level:

- Base level.

Limitations and Constraints

The provisioning of the service under the agreed service level targets is subject to the following limitations and constraints:

- Support is provided in English
- Downtimes caused due to upgrades for fixing critical security issues are not considered Agreement violations:
 - A security issue is one where the service offered to a user is compromised by the activity of another user or external actors
- Force Majeure:
 - Any party's failure to perform any term or condition of this Agreement as a result of circumstances beyond the control of the relevant party (including without limitation war, strikes, flood, governmental restrictions, and power, telecommunications or internet failures, or damages to or destruction of any network facilities) ('Force Majeure') shall not be deemed to be, or to give rise to, a breach of this Agreement
 - If any party to this Agreement is prevented or delayed in the performance of any of its obligations under this Agreement by Force Majeure, and if this party gives written notice thereof to the other party specifying the matters constituting Force Majeure together with such evidence as it reasonably can give and specifying the period for which it is estimated that such prevention or delay will continue, then the party in question shall be excused of the performance or the punctual performance of any of its obligations from the date of such notice for so long as the Force Majeure is in effect.

Communication, Reporting and Escalation

General Communication

The following contacts will be generally used for communications related to the service in the scope of this Agreement:

EOSC Future contact	Matthew Viljoen < matthew.viljoen@egi.eu >
Service owner contact	Gareth O'Neill Technopolis Group Belgium < gareth.oneill@technopolis-group.com > Natalia Manola OpenAIRE < natalia.manola@openaire.eu >

Support contact	Stefania Martziou OpenAIRE < stefania.martziou@openaire.eu >
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Regular Reporting

As part of the fulfilment of this Agreement and provisioning of the service, the following reports will be created as part of the service management. Performance reports are created on a daily basis by the EOSC Monitoring service [<https://eosccore.ui.argo.grnet.gr>] as a result of the regular monitoring tests executed against the service and are aggregated into monthly performance reports [<https://eosccore.ui.argo.grnet.gr/eosccore/report-ar/CORE/SITES>]. The produced reports will be used to verify the fulfilment of the service level targets on a monthly basis.

Violations

The service supplier commits to inform the T7.4 task leader if this Agreement is violated or if violation is anticipated. The following rules are agreed for communication in the event of a violation:

- In case of any violation of the service targets, the service supplier will provide justifications and a plan for service enhancement to the T7.4 task leader
- The EOSC Future supplier management staff will notify the service supplier in case of a monitored potential violation via the EOSC helpdesk. The case will be analysed to identify the cause and verify the violation.

Escalation and Complaints

For escalation and complaints, the service owner contacts will be used and the following rules will apply:

- In case of repeated violation of the service targets for two consecutive months or four months in a reporting period, a review of the Agreement and of the service enhancement plan will take place involving the parties of the Agreement
- Complaints or concerns about the service should be directed to the service owner contacts who will promptly address these concerns. Should there still be dissatisfaction about either the result of the response or the behaviour of the service supplier, the Technical Coordination Board <tcb@eoscfuture.eu> will be informed.

Information Security and Data Protection

The following rules for information security and data protection apply:

- The service supplier agrees to take appropriate technical and organisational measures, based on a risk-management approach, to protect data and infrastructure and to minimise possible harm in the event of a security incident (e.g. a personal data breach or hacking)

- The service supplier will abide by the EOSC Security Operational Baseline [<https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCSMS/EOSC+Security+Operational+Baseline>]
- The service supplier will define and abide by an information security and data protection policy related to the service being provided
- The security and data protection policies of the supplier must comply with all EOSC Future policies and procedures and also must be compliant with relevant national legislation (i.e. services to be legal in the jurisdiction under which they operate). The EOSC Future Data Protection Policy [<https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/x/yYI8AQ>] is specified in the Data Protection Management System (DPMS)
- The service supplier shall provide a notice to data subjects that is compliant with data protection laws, for instance based on the AARC PDK [<https://aarc-project.eu/policies/policy-development-kit>] template. The structure of the notice should be comparable for all services
- The service supplier will enforce the EOSC Future WISE Acceptable Usage Policies [<https://wise-community.org/wise-baseline-aup>]
- The service supplier will comply with all principles set out by the REFEDS Data Protection Code of Conduct [<https://wiki.refeds.org/display/CODE/Code+of+Conduct+2.0>].

Responsibilities

Of the Service Supplier

Additional responsibilities of the service supplier are as follows:

- Adhere to all applicable operational and security policies and procedures, as well as to other policy documents referenced therein
- Use the communication channel defined in the agreement (e.g. either the helpdesk or the email addresses listed above)
- Attend T7.4 meetings and other operations meetings when requested by the EOSC Future contact. A representative may be nominated should the assigned person be unavailable.

If delivering software as a service, the additional responsibilities of the service supplier are as follows:

- A service with associated roles is registered in the GOCDB.

Of EOSC Future

The responsibilities include:

- Raise any issues deemed necessary to the attention of the service supplier
- Collect requirements from users
- Support coordination with other EOSC Future services
- Provide monitoring and a helpdesk to measure fulfilment of agreed service level targets
- Create and provide service reports based on the Agreement.

Review, Extensions, and Termination

There will be reviews of the service performance against service level targets and of this Agreement at planned intervals with EOSC Future according to the following rules:

- Technical content of the Agreement and targets will be reviewed on a yearly basis.